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FUNDAMENTALS OF LITERACY AND CHILD COGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to analyze the relationship between the foundations of literacy and children's cognitive development , highlighting the use of digital games as a support tool for pedagogical and inclusive practices . It is based on the premise that literacy is not limited to the mechanical mastery of reading and writing but is a complex process involving essential cognitive functions such as attention , memory , perception , and language . The study adopts a qualitative approach through a bibliographic review , drawing on authors who discuss neuroscience , cognitive processes, and contemporary educational practices . The findings suggest that when digital resources are integrated in a planned manner and mediated by trained professionals , they foster meaningful learning and contribute to the child's overall development . In this context , digital games emerge as promising tools that stimulate essential cognitive skills in a playful and interactive way , increasing student engagement and expanding inclusion possibilities within the school environment . The article thus advocates for the critical and conscious integration of digital technologies into educational practices , promoting more effective and meaningful literacy .

Keywords : Literacy . Cognitive development . Digital games. Cognitive processes. Early childhood education .

1. INTRODUCTION

Early literacy is a complex process that goes beyond simple letter and sound recognition, involving a set of fundamental cognitive skills such as attention, memory,

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language, and perception. In an educational landscape increasingly influenced by technology, new possibilities for supporting learning through digital resources, especially educational games, emerge.

Technological resources offer great potential for a more dynamic, interactive, and inclusive literacy process when used in a planned manner and with the appropriate guidance of trained professionals. Considering the challenges educators face in promoting meaningful learning from the earliest school years, it is essential to understand the relationship between the foundations of literacy and children's cognitive development. Therefore, it is crucial to stimulate children's executive functions early on through playful and contextualized experiences that foster emotional engagement and logical reasoning.

Through a bibliographic review focusing on authors from the fields of neuroscience, psychopedagogy, and education, this article proposes to analyze how digital games can act as effective tools in strengthening functions and, consequently, in literacy.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study is a qualitative, descriptive, and analytical literature review. The materials were selected through searches in recognized scientific databases such as SciELO, Google Scholar, ResearchGate, Redalyc, and the CAPES Journal Portal, as well as proceedings of specialized conferences such as the Brazilian Congress on Informatics in Education (CBIE) and the Brazilian Symposium on Informatics in Education (SBIE).

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The inclusion criteria were the relevance of topics related to the fundamentals of literacy, child cognitive development, and the use of digital technologies in the educational process. The analysis of the selected texts followed an interpretive approach, seeking to connect theoretical concepts to practical contexts, with an emphasis on understanding how digital games contribute to the development of essential cognitive functions in the literacy process.

3. DEVELOPMENT

3.1. Cognitive Processes in Early Childhood Literacy

Successful literacy acquisition in children in the early years is directly related to the proper development of cognitive functions such as attention, memory, language, reasoning, and perception, as well as executive functions such as planning, inhibitory control, working memory, cognitive flexibility, and problem-solving. These functions, in turn, aid in the identification and understanding of symbols, so essential for learning to read and write.

According to Lains and Rocha (2020), pedagogical practices that aim to stimulate attention favor the literacy process, allowing the child to understand visual and sound patterns, remember rules and still maintain focus.

Costa et al. (2018) point out that digital games can improve cognitive functions such as attention, memory, and reasoning, through activities that connect images and words. Eugênio and Hennemann (2024) emphasize that gamified games improve focus,

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problem-solving, and decision-making. These games encourage the use of strategies, review of hypotheses, and reflection on mistakes and successes during the game.

Habowski and Ratto (2024) emphasize that digital games, by promoting children's emotional engagement in a motivating environment, also provide significant improvements in cognitive functions, further favoring concentration and persistence.

Ramos et al. (2020) emphasize that well-designed digital games develop students' sustained attention and working memory. However, pedagogical mediation by trained professionals is essential to ensure these resources meet students' individual needs. Educators must also understand the relationship between literacy and cognitive development to use them effectively.

Deitos and Aragón (2021) state that literacy goes beyond memorizing letters, being a gradual process dependent on neurological maturation and the pedagogical environment. Neves (2023) points out that multisensory and playful experiences activate brain areas, promoting meaningful learning.

The program "Neurons and the Jewels of Knowledge," cited by Eugênio and Hennemann (2024), demonstrates improvements in reading and writing through reasoning, focus, and emotional control. Lains and Rocha (2020) emphasize that the use of digital games, when contextualized in well-planned pedagogical practices, strengthens emotional self-regulation and facilitates reading and writing. Also according to Lains and Rocha (2020), sustained attention can be developed with games that require prolonged concentration.

Habowski and Ratto (2024) and Ramos et al. (2020) highlight that games with engaging scripts promote memorization, engagement, and inhibitory control. Integrating

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digital games into the literacy process therefore stimulates cognitive development and essential skills for school and social life.

3.2. Phonological Awareness and Learning to Read

Phonological awareness is the ability to recognize, analyze, and manipulate speech sounds. It is essential for reading and writing because it aids in text decoding. Prado and Ramos (2021) emphasize that digital games are effective for developing reading skills by promoting dynamic associations between phonemes and graphemes. The playfulness of games motivates students and allows for the repeated practice of phonological skills in an engaged manner.

Neves (2023) emphasizes that games facilitate learning by promoting greater student engagement and interpersonal engagement. Santos and Silva (2022) demonstrate that games that use visual and auditory stimuli promote improvements in students' identification of syllables and phonemes. This approach is aligned with multimedia learning theory according to Stafusa et al. (2020).

Lima, Menezes, and Serra (2024) emphasize the importance of games for students with intellectual disabilities because they take into account each student's learning pace. Araújo Correio and Sales Correio (2020) point out similar benefits for children with ADHD, such as improved attention and inhibitory control.

In addition to phonological awareness, digital games also improve executive functions such as working memory and attention. Eugênio and Hennemann (2024) demonstrate these gains in students with attention difficulties. Cerqueira et al. (2018)

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also indicate that inhibitory control can be stimulated by games that require quick decisions and selective attention.

Alves (2008) demonstrates that frequent video game players perform better in sustained attention, which is essential for literacy. Ramos et al. (2016) state that digital games promote social interactions, which are important for the development of oral language and reading.

For Ramos, Loreset , and Petri (2016), games create a sensory-rich environment that activates brain areas related to memory, attention, and language. However, Deitos and Aragón (2021) warn that the use of digital technologies in literacy instruction must consider students' particularities to promote inclusion and effectiveness.

Costa et al. (2018) suggest that game design should integrate clear pedagogical objectives. Thus, digital educational games become innovative tools for addressing common literacy challenges, such as demotivation and lack of attention, in addition to providing more meaningful and inclusive learning.

3.3.Attention and Inhibitory Control in School-Age Children

The early years of elementary school are characterized by demanding more of children's cognitive functions, as they are forced to maintain focus, follow rules, and resist impulses. For Ramos et al. (2017), attention and inhibitory control are prerequisites for reading, writing, and logical reasoning, as they involve the ability to filter out irrelevant stimuli and inhibit automatic responses.

Araújo Correio and Sales Correio (2020) note that difficulties in cognitive functions can manifest as inattention, impulsivity, and low performance, often confused

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with disinterest. In cases like ADHD, the use of adapted pedagogical strategies is essential.

In this context, digital games emerge as innovative tools for developing attention and self-regulation, offering progressive challenges in a playful environment that encourages focus, persistence, and self-control. Ramos et al. (2020) highlight that gamified games promote improvements in executive functions by requiring quick decisions, monitoring, and impulse inhibition.

These games also offer immediate feedback and adapt to the child's particularities, promoting engagement and personalized learning. Cerqueira, Barbosa, and Mossman (2018) emphasize that digital games, by providing varied sensory stimuli, favor the strengthening of inhibitory control in children.

In regular education and Specialized Educational Services (SEAs), digital games have also shown positive impact. Ramos and Garcia (2019) demonstrated behavioral and academic improvements in children with learning disabilities after implementing structured game programs. However, their effectiveness depends on qualified pedagogical mediation. According to Ramos et al. (2018), educators must ensure the intentional use of games, aligning them with learning objectives.

Studies such as those by Alves (2008) and Santos et al. (2024) confirm that, when well-designed, digital games improve selective and sustained attention, and impulse control. Frequent players of educational games performed better in these areas compared to non-players.

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In literacy, Neves (2023) and Lima, Menezes and Serra (2024) emphasize that attention is fundamental and that children who can focus on classroom instructions, inhibit impulses and review actions tend to perform better in reading and writing.

Costa, Dias, and Santos (2022) add that digital games have varying levels of difficulty, which favors a more inclusive and accessible learning environment. In short, attention and inhibitory control are central to child development, and with qualified mediation, digital games represent an effective strategy for promoting quality learning and the comprehensive development of students.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results show that the planned use of digital games in early literacy instruction favors the development of essential cognitive functions, such as attention, memory, and language. These resources, when properly mediated by educators, promote meaningful learning, emotional engagement, and inclusion, especially for children with cognitive difficulties. The research reinforces that technology, integrated with sound pedagogical practices, contributes to more effective, playful literacy instruction, adapted to the needs of the 21st century.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the study carried out, it is possible to affirm that the foundations of literacy are deeply interconnected with the development of cognitive functions in childhood, especially those related to attention, memory, perception, language and

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inhibitory control, which makes such elements indispensable for the ability to read and write.

The use of digital games in educational settings, when intentionally planned and aligned with pedagogical objectives, significantly contributes to strengthening these cognitive processes. The playfulness, progressive challenges, and immediate feedback provided by digital games not only foster student engagement but also the development of fundamental learning skills such as focus, self-regulation, decision-making, and cognitive flexibility.

Technological resources should be seen as allies in promoting more inclusive education, as they allow for adaptations that respect students' different learning rhythms and styles, including those with cognitive difficulties, learning disabilities, or specific educational needs. Investing in teacher training for the pedagogical use of technologies, based on the principles of neuroscience and psychopedagogy, is a necessary and urgent strategy to meet the demands of contemporary education.

Therefore, it is concluded that the integration between mediated pedagogical practices, cognitive development and digital resources represents a promising path to make the literacy process more efficient, meaningful and aligned with the challenges of the 21st century.

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